

CONTENTMENT OF PATIENTS TOWARDS THE SERVICES RENDERED IN THE HEALTH CARE SECTOR – A CASE STUDY

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Abstract:

In India hospital industry is growing at a very faster rate. Diseases are increasing in a rapid manner due to because of negligence of the people i.e. improper diet, no physical work, junk foods etc., and leads to spoil the health of the people. In this connection people are visiting the hospitals frequently. The crowds in the hospitals are increasing, but some of the hospitals are unable to provide proper facilities to the visitors of their hospitals. That is why the researcher has chosen the present topic in order to evaluate the satisfaction level of the patients towards the services provided by the selected research unit. Primary data has been collected from the respondents through a well structured questionnaire. Secondary data has been gathered from the journals, magazines, internet etc. Statistical tools like percentage analysis; tabulation etc has been used to analyze the raw data of the present study. The current study is an attempt of the researcher to evaluate the contentment of patients towards the services rendered by the selected hospital in the modern society.

Key Words: Contentment, Services, Hospital & Patients.

Introduction:

In the new millennium, the biggest management challenge of liberalization and globalization for a business is to serve and maintain good relations with the king, the customer. In the past, producers took their customers for granted, because at that time customers were not demanding nor did they have many alternative sources of supply or suppliers. Since the customer was passive customer, the producer dictated terms and had very little customer commitment. But today, there is a radical transformation. The changing business environment is characterized by economic liberalization, increasing competition, high consumer choice, enlightened and demanding customer, more emphasis on quality and value of purchases etc.

Results and Discussion:

Socio Economic Profile of Respondents:

Patients play a significant role in influencing the effective functioning of an organization/Hospital. The quality of services by the Hospital and the consequent image or good will created in the eyes of public at large depends on the efficiency with which the personnel perform the tasks. In view of the significant role of personnel in the effective functioning of organization, it would be fruitful to examine and understand their socio-economic characteristics that influences, in a large measure of, their behaviour and performance.

1. Age:

Age has influence on one's own life. As age advances the maturity of an individual increases. The attitude, mental maturity, exposure, individuality and the behaviour pattern of a person varies with advancement in the age. Productivity also said to be a function of age. During youth men and women are in full of vigour and vitality, the achievement level of productivity at work place is naturally high. However, it cannot be totally rejected that the productivity is inversely related to age. In other words as age advances, normally, productivity per person decreases and vice-versa. The age distribution of the respondents is presented in table No.1.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample According to Age

S.No	Age-Group	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	20 & Below	07	1.55
2	21 – 30	46	10.22
3	31 – 40	68	15.11
4	41 – 50	143	31.77
5	51 – 60	186	41.35
	Total	450	100.00

It is evident that the highest number of respondents (41.35 percent) belonging to the age group of 51-60. Because of age factor they are suffering from various diseases like cancer, diabetes, kidney problems etc. This is followed by the age group of 41-50 which constitutes 31.77 percent of the respondents. Similarly 10.22 percent of the respondents fall in age group of 21-30. From the above it is clear that a few respondents fall under the age group of 21-30.

Chart 1: Distribution of Sample According to Age

2. Gender:

Traditionally most of the women in India are confined to kitchen and other domestic activities. Very recently, they are coming out of the kitchen burrows and also seeking employment in order to supplement to their family income. Still for obvious reasons, the employment of women in the country is not encouraging. But in the present study the females proportion in the total respondents is merely 63.77 percent (table 2).

Table: 2 Distribution of Sample According to Sex

S.No	Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Male	163	36.23
2.	Female	287	63.77
	Total	450	100.00

Chart 2: Distribution of Sample According to Sex

The proportion of female respondents is very high i.e.63.77 percent of the total and it is a clear evidence of female domination. It may be because of nature of work in the organization i.e. technical, loading and unloading activities, working at open places having exposure to hot sun etc. Female employees are found only in non-technical jobs, such as medical department, clerical and ministerial staff in the administrative office.

3. Religion:

Religion plays an important role in the human civilization and culture. It is felt that religious affiliation of employees will have influences on their work behaviour and performance. It could be observed from that data presented in the table that the respondents mostly belong to Hindu religion (74.75 per cent). The predominant Hindu population in this state has been reflected among the employees selected for study. Table no. 3 presents the distribution of respondents by religion.

Table 3: Religion – Wise Distribution of Respondents

S.No	Religion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Hindus	304	75.55
2.	Muslims	68	15.11
3.	Christians	87	19.33
4.	Others	09	02.00
	Total :	450	100.00

Chart 3: Religion – Wise Distribution of Respondents

It is quite natural that around 75.55 percent of the country’s population belongs to Hindu religion. Therefore, the sample also mostly represents Hindus. This is followed by Christians forming 19.33% percent of the respondents, Muslims (15.11percent) and others (2.05 percent) such as Sikhs, Jains, etc.

4. Caste:

Caste system is the most important and utmost universal basis of social stratification of Hindu Society. Though its binding force is diminishing in social communication and outward behaviour, still it is a potent favour in influencing social values, customs, marriage relations etc. The economic and cultural life of people has roots in their caste and social background². In India, for centuries the people of Hindu religion have been divided into various castes depending on the nature of their profession. This situation had led the emergence of several castes. It is a sorrow state of affairs that people belong to some castes is still leading an isolated life without access to several resources of the country. In order to uplift the down-trodden and ill-fated people belonging to lower order caste groups, viz., Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and listed Backward Classes, the Government has reserved a certain proportion of jobs in all PSE’s, Government Officers and Government aided agencies and institutions. Around half of the respondents have been reserved for all these groups of people. It is observed from the data furnished in the table no. 3.5 that the employment of SC & ST’s is marginally lower than the percentage of stipulated reservation where as the proportion of LBC’s is four percent higher than its stipulated reservation. Of course, the objective of reservation, of jobs to these sections of population is to provide employment to the minimum level of 22 percent for SC & ST’s, 25 percent to LBC groups of people.

Table 4: Caste Wise Distribution of Sample

S.No	Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	SC	85	18.88
2.	ST	89	19.77
3.	BC	32	7.13
4.	FC	244	54.22
	Total :	450	100.00

Chart 4: Caste Wise Distribution of Sample

The above table reveals that half of the respondents belong to Forward Caste. This is followed by SC/ST 38.65 per cent and BC's 7.13 per cent of the sample. From the above it is clear that majority of the respondents belong to FC (i.e. 244 respondents).

5. Marital Status:

Marriage is an important event in one's life. Marriage is treated as an important social institution in India. But its form and functions may change according to the socio-cultural environment of the society. Marriage in India is considered as a religious sacrament in which a man and a woman are bound in permanent relationship for the physical, social and spiritual purposes, sexual pleasure and procreation. It influences the style of living and also the attitude, disposition and commitment towards work. Sometimes, matters relating to their household also affect the state of mind of the employees at work.

Table 5: Marital Status of the Respondents

S.No	Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Married	392	90.06
2	Un-Married	58	9.94
3	Separated	00	00.00
4	Widow/ Widower	00	00.00
	Total :	450	100.00

Chart 5: Marital Status of the Respondents

Table 5 shows that ninety per cent (392) of the respondents were married and the rest are unmarried. No case of separation and Widow/Widower has been noticed among the selected respondents.

It is also observed that all the women respondents have got married and hence it could be inferred that all unmarried respondents are males. Personal interviews with the unmarried respondents reveal that they did not marry because (a) most of them are eldest earning members of the family having responsibility of performing marriage of their sisters; (b) some of them are only earning members having obligation of taking care of educational needs of their younger brothers and/or sisters; (c) to redeem the debt obligations of the family. It is the culture of the eastern countries especially in India in the absence of the parents or the earnings of the father is not enough to discharge the family obligations, the son(s) of the family take the responsibility and postpone the decision of marriage until he/they fulfill those obligations.

6. Dependents:

The number of dependents will have a bearing on the economic conditions of the employees. It is natural that higher the number of dependents, higher would be financial burden on the family. It is pertinent to mention here that the observation of Morse study of white-collar workers. Indicates that the "more dependents one has, the less satisfaction he has with the job". The numbers of dependents to those respondents are presented in table no. 6.

Table 6: Number of Dependents

S.No	No. of Dependents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Below 3	219	60.26
2	3 To 5	135	29.96
3	5 To 8	96	9.78
4	8 To 10	00	00.00
	Total :	450	100.00

Chart 6: Number of Dependents

It can be seen from the table that 219 respondents (60.26 per cent) has less than three dependents, 29.96 per cent of the respondents have three to five dependents and 9.78 per cent of the respondents have five to eight dependents. On average the respondents have had three dependents. It is notable that no respondent is free from dependent in the family. This reflects typical and true Indian family system. Husbands takes up wage employment or earn through some economic activity wife stays at home looking after household duties and the children get education depending on the income of the parent. In some cases the son (s) even after completion of graduation/ post graduation may depend on parent as he could not secure some gainful employment.

7. Education:

Education plays an important role in determining one’s socio-economic status in the entire society. It should be noted that education is a pre-requisite for progress and development of an individual. The high incidence of illiteracy amongst people constitutes one of the greatest barriers to their development. It limits the scope of employment, training, and utilization of health facilities and exercise of legal and constitutional rights.

Educational qualification forms an important basis in hiring of employees in an organization. The qualifications differ from job to job and also from position to position. The educational qualifications of the respondents are shown in table 7.

Table 7: Educational Qualifications of Respondents

S.No	Educational Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Illiterate	-	-
2.	Primary	45	9.93
3.	Secondary	223	49.66
4.	Intermediate	47	10.59
5.	Diploma	90	19.86
6.	Degree & P.G	22	4.96
7.	Professionals	23	5.00
	Total	450	100.00

Chart 7: Educational Qualifications of Respondents

It is revealed that out of 450 respondents, 60 respondents (9.93 percent) have got primary education. Majority of respondents (300) have got secondary school level education. This group constitutes 49.66 percent of the total. 64 respondents (10.59 per cent) have studied Intermediate (10 +2) level. One-fifth of the respondents (20 percent) acquired Diploma. 30 respondents (5 percent) are graduates and Postgraduates and another 30 respondents (5 percent) have acquired professional qualifications. Hence, from this table it can be concluded that more than 50 per cent of respondents and employees class III and IV workers. These posts need minimum education; as such 50 per cent of respondents are possessing secondary school certificate.

Findings:

- ✓ The study reveals that the respondents felt that courtesy is one of the important elements in the hospital which is to be followed by the hospital personnel.
- ✓ Respondents also felt that the hospitals should follow the feedback mechanism in order to protect the interests of the visitors of the hospital.
- ✓ Visitors of the hospital opined that the top level management should maintain complaint box to solve the problems of the patient's etc.

Conclusion:

Amenities may raise a similar measurement problem: if hospitals are providing more amenities and a better experience, then estimates of inflation of health care costs would arguably be biased upward, since price indexes don't account for amenities. But if amenities are important — and aren't included in performance assessments - then the productivity of hospitals that offer greater amenities is being understated. Hospitals that are focused on this part of the patient experience may therefore suffer under the new law. If the services offered by the hospitals are in a satisfied manner the business of the hospital will grow which in turn leads to earn more profits.

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